

A Recommender Agent to Support Virtual Learning Activities

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Abstract : This article describes the implementation of an intelligent agent that provides recommendations for educational resources in a virtual learning environment (VLE). It aims to support pending (undeveloped) student learning activities. It begins by analyzing the proposed VLE data model entities in the recommender process. The pending student activities are then identified, which constitutes the input information for the agent. By using the attribute-based recommender technique, the information can be processed and resource recommendations can be obtained. These serve as a support for pending activity development in the course. To integrate this technique, we used an ontology. This serves as support for the semantic annotation of attributes and recommended files recovery.

Keywords : learning activities, educational resource, recommender agent, recommendation technique, ontology.

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